

Effects of Light Deprivation on Closed Aquatic Ecosystems: A Longitudinal Experimental Study

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Abstract

Light is one of the main factors that condition the functioning of ecosystems, directly influencing photosynthesis and, consequently, the dynamics of biological communities. The present study aimed to evaluate the effects of the absence of light in closed aquatic ecosystems. Two similar aquatic ecosystems were prepared containing water, sediments, aquatic organisms, and specimens of *Sphagnum cuspidatum*.

One of the ecosystems was maintained under normal lighting conditions (control), while the other was maintained in the absence of light for 24 days. Throughout the study, periodic macroscopic and microscopic observations were carried out, as well as analyses of the color and luminosity of the ecosystems and the pigments extracted from the plant tissues.

The results demonstrated that the absence of light caused the progressive loss of photosynthetic activity, the degradation of plant tissues, the appearance of surface biofilms, the increase in the activity of decomposer organisms, and changes in the composition of photosynthetic pigments. In the lightless ecosystem, the accumulation of decomposing organic matter, increased turbidity, and mortality of various organisms were also observed.

It is concluded that the absence of light leads to the progressive degradation of the closed aquatic ecosystem, causing a reduction in primary producers and favoring the activity of decomposers. The results obtained corroborate the initial hypothesis and highlight the importance of light for maintaining the ecological balance of these systems.

Introduction

Aquatic ecosystems are complex systems that exhibit great biodiversity, ranging from microorganisms such as bacteria to larger organisms such as vertebrates. Aquatic ecosystems play essential roles in biogeochemical cycles and ecological balance. At the base of aquatic ecosystems are microorganisms such as bacteria, protozoa, and algae. These are fundamental in decomposition, photosynthesis, and food chains.

By using closed aquatic ecosystems in a controlled environment, we are able to observe the different interactions between living beings, and between living beings and the environment.

Light radiation plays an important role in ecosystems, being vital in photosynthesis, the process by which autotrophic organisms obtain matter. Since these organisms are the basis of the ecosystem, as they are the producers, if autotrophic organisms are affected, the entire ecosystem is also affected.

This study aims to understand how the absence of light affects aquatic ecosystems, through microscopic and macroscopic and chemical analysis of closed aquatic ecosystems subjected to light conditions similar to nature, and to the total absence of light.

Objectives and Hypothesis

Light is essential for photosynthesis, and photosynthetic autotrophs depend on it to obtain organic matter. All other levels in food chains depend on the matter produced by these organisms. Consequently, light influences the entire ecosystem.

This experiment aims to understand how ecosystems behave when subjected to a complete absence of light.

Our hypothesis is that the absence of light radiation in a closed ecosystem can cause producers to undergo progressive die-off. With the extinction of the producers, the rest of the community also slowly dies out, with decomposers being the last to perish. We can also expect changes in water pH due to decomposer activity (processes such as humification and the production of ammonia, carbon dioxide, and hydrogen sulfide, among other decomposition products).

Experimental Procedure

For this experiment, we used:

- Two plastic bottles
- Compound light microscope
- Pasteur pipettes
- Slides and coverslips
- Funnel
- Mobile phone
- Filter paper
- 70% ethyl alcohol
- Forceps and spatula

1. We wrote a letter on both containers—on the lid and on the container itself. We wrote the letter A on one container and the letter B on the other. Container A served as our control, exposed to light conditions similar to those found in nature. Container B was the one subjected to complete darkness.

2. We arrived at the collection site (a small stream) and placed water, soil, organic matter, and aquatic plants into both containers. It is important to note that the container should not be completely filled with water; an empty space must be left to allow for an “atmosphere” within the simulated ecosystem.

1. Sample collection site.

3. Both containers are stabilized for a period of 5 hours before data collection begins.

2. Containers already containing the samples, at the collection site, having not yet undergone the stabilization process.

3. Containers after the stabilization process.

4. After the stabilization period, both containers are analyzed macroscopically and microscopically, chemically, and in terms of color (lightness and percentage proportions of red, green, and blue). Photographs are taken for comparison purposes in subsequent phases.

5. The containers are analyzed in a similar manner at 4-day intervals (days 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, and 24 of the experiment).

Observations and Results

Samples were collected on the first day. Before the stabilization period, the water was turbid, but after this interval, it became much clearer (Figures 2 and 3).

The simulated ecosystem is characterized by a gravel substrate. It contains aquatic plants notably *Ceratophyllum submersum* and *Sphagnum cuspidatum* as well as arthropods, such as aquatic beetles (family Gyrinidae), and what appear to be aquatic annelids.

5. *Sphagnum cuspidatum*

6. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* under the light microscope (100x magnification).

7. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* under the microscope (300x magnification).

Fig.8 *Ceratophyllum submersum*

9. *Ceratophyllum submersum* under the microscope (100x magnification).

10. Beetle of the family Gyrinidae.

When performing a color analysis using the Color Grab app, the results were as follows:

For both Flask A and Flask B, the values are similar, with an average red proportion of 45.4967%, an average green proportion of 42.327%, and an average blue proportion of 12.1763%.

Regarding turbidity, both flasks show a lightness value of approximately 77.1%. The analysis is conducted by selecting 10 points on the image and calculating the average of the analyzed values.

On the fourth day, we performed the second analysis.

11. The two flasks, B (flask without light) and A (control).

Upon opening, flask B emitted a strong odor. Flask A did not emit any odor. In flask B, the majority of the arthropods were found at the surface.

Following this observation, we removed samples of *Sphagnum cuspidatum* from both flasks and prepared microscope slides.

The tissues from the control were fully functional, and photosynthesis was observed.

12. Slide with *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissue from flask A.

13. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues observed under a light microscope (100x magnification).

14. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues and two air bubbles formed by photosynthesis carried out by them (100x magnification).

In the tissues collected in flask B, however, it was not possible to observe photosynthesis, and we saw some dark spots on these tissues.

15. Slide with *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissue collected in vial B.

16. Spots on the *Sphagnum cuspidatum* sample collected in flask B (100x magnification).

17. Spots on the *Sphagnum cuspidatum* sample collected in flask B (300x magnification).

We also conducted a separate experiment with the *Sphagnum cuspidatum* samples. We began by breaking up the samples and placing them in beakers containing 70% ethyl alcohol.

18. Tissue + ethyl alcohol (70%) solution in flask A, on the left, and in flask B, on the right.

We let the alcohol act for one hour, and then filtered the solutions.

19. Control and flask B solutions, respectively, after filtration.

Comparing the color of both filtered solutions, we observe that the solution in A exhibits a light green hue, indicating the presence of intact photosynthetic pigments—specifically chlorophylls—whereas the solution in B displays a yellowish-greenish-brown hue, indicating the presence of degraded photosynthetic pigments and degradation products.

We analyzed the color using the Color Grab app, and the results were as follows:

In container A, the average proportion of red is 45.2486%, the average proportion of green is 41.4726%, and the average proportion of blue is 13.2788%. The luminosity is approximately 70.4%.

In container B, the average proportion of red is 47.0659%, the average proportion of green is 39.5039%, and the average proportion of blue is 13.4301%. The luminosity is approximately 61.7%.

On the eighth day, we performed the third complete analysis.

20. Flasks A and B, respectively, on the 8th day of the study.

Flask B emitted a stronger odor than last time, and almost all the arthropods were found at the surface. Upon microscopic examination of *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues, we noticed that the tissue in Flask B appeared lifeless, ranging in color from transparent to yellow, whereas the tissue in Flask A was green. We also observed small black spots on the leaves in Flask A, which did not appear to affect the plant.

21. Slide with *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissue samples from flask A and flask B (respectively).

22. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from the control (100x magnification).

23. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from the control (300x magnification).

24. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from the control (600x magnification).

25. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from Flask B (100x magnification).

26. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from Flask B (300x magnification).

.27 *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from Flask B (600x magnification).

We also conducted color tests, using the previous procedures.

28. Pigment solutions from flasks A and B (respectively) before being filtered.

29. Pigmented solutions of A and B (respectively), after filtration.

The analysis results were as follows:

The pigments in vial A show an average red proportion of 37.955%, an average green proportion of 36.1758%, and an average blue proportion of 25.8691%; the average luminosity is 66.7%.

The pigments in vial B show an average red proportion of 40.8318%, an average green proportion of 35.3767%, and an average blue proportion of 23.7915%; the average luminosity is 45.5%.

On the 12th day, we performed the fourth analysis.

30. Flasks A and B (respectively), on day 12.

We removed *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from both flasks and analyzed them under the microscope.

31. Slide prepared with *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from the Control and Flask B (respectively).

In the control, the tissues remain functional, whereas in flask B the tissues are dead and many more ciliated protozoa can be observed. On the surface of flask B, we also observed that most of the arthropods were dead.

32. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from the control (100x magnification).

33. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from the control (300x magnification).

34. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from flask B (100x magnification).

35. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from flask B (300x magnification).

36. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from flask B (600x magnification).

We extracted pigments from both tissues.

The pigments in vial A show an average red proportion of 42.835%, an average green proportion of 40.9243%, and an average blue proportion of 16.2406%; the average luminosity is 88.1%.

The pigments in vial B show an average red proportion of 41.8373%, an average green proportion of 39.1543%, and an average blue proportion of 18.9817%; the average luminosity is 56.1%.

On the 16th day, we performed the fifth analysis.

37. Control and Vial B on day 16.

In flask B, the odor emitted is strong, and we observe the formation of biofilms on the surface.

38. Biofilms on the surface of flask B.

We also examined *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from both flasks.

39. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from the control (100x magnification).

40. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from the control (300x magnification).

41. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from the control (600x magnification).

The samples from flask B exhibit higher microorganism activity.

42. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from flask B (100x magnification).

43. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from flask B (300x magnification).

42. *Sphagnum cuspidatum* tissues from flask B (600x magnification).

We extracted pigments from both tissues.

The pigments from vial A show an average red proportion of 46.1363%, an average green proportion of 39.1251%, and an average blue proportion of 14.7446%; the average luminosity is 74.7%.

The pigments from vial B show an average red proportion of 47.0717%, an average green proportion of 36.8960%, and an average blue proportion of 16.0322%; the average luminosity is 58.2%.

On the 20th, we conducted the 6th analysis. In flask B, we observed more developed biofilms and increased clarity due to the sedimentation of residues resulting from decomposition.

43. Vial A and Vial B, respectively, on day 20.

We extracted pigments from both fabrics.

The pigments from vial A show an average red proportion of 46.1876%, an average green proportion of 41.9366%, and an average blue proportion of 11.8758%; the average luminosity is 75.2%.

The pigments from vial B show an average red proportion of 44.6496%, an average green proportion of 38.3329%, and an average blue proportion of 17.0176%; the average luminosity is 61.1%.

44. Pigmented solutions from vial A and B, respectively.

On the 24th day, we performed the seventh analysis.

45. Flask B and Control, respectively, on day 24.

In flask B, the plant tissues, which appear to be metabolically inactive, accumulate at the bottom, with the ecosystem's water consisting of a suspension of dead tissues and decomposition products. The surface biofilm is much more developed, and the flask continues to emit a strong odor.

We also extracted pigments from *Sphagnum cuspidatum* from both flasks.

46. Pigmented solutions from flask A and flask B, respectively, on the 24th day of observation.

The pigments in bottle A show an average red proportion of 47.4182%, an average green proportion of 42.1195%, and an average blue proportion of 10.4624%; the average luminosity is 67.6%.

The pigments in bottle B show an average red proportion of 47.575%, an average green proportion of 36.1552%, and an average blue proportion of 16.2698%; the average luminosity is 58.4%.

Discussion

The study aimed to understand the effects of the absence of light on closed ecosystems. We hypothesized that, over time, the ecosystem subjected to the absence of light would degrade, specifically, that the number of producers would decrease while the number of decomposers would increase. We observed this process throughout the study.

The absence of light had a significant impact on ecosystem B. The water became much more turbid; however, turbidity decreased during the final days of the study due to the sedimentation of decomposition products that had previously been suspended in the water column. Variations in light levels occurred in the control group, with a drop in the final days likely caused by an increase in plant biomass within the system.

47. Graph showing the luminosity rate as a function of time for both flasks.

Over time, we also observe a relatively variable decrease in the percentage of green in the pigmented solutions of flask B, due to the partial extinction of the producers.

48. Graph showing the percentage concentration of green as a function of time, for the Control and flask B.

Regarding the blue concentration in the solutions, we observed that the concentration in both flasks peaked on day 8; thereafter, the concentration decreased, although at the end of the study, it was higher in Flask B than in the Control.

49. Graph showing the relationship between the blue concentration in the Control and in flask B and time in days.

Regarding the percentage concentration of red, it varies, being slightly higher in Flask B than in the Control at the end of the study.

50. Graph relating the red concentration to the time interval, in days.

In conclusion, the study allows us to understand how the absence of light influences an ecosystem.

Producers die due to the absence of light. This occurs because light is necessary for the photochemical phase of photosynthesis. Without this phase, photosynthesis does not take place, nor does the production of organic matter required for the producers' metabolism. This phenomenon directly affects consumers, as they depend on the organic matter synthesized by producers; without it, they cannot survive.

In the absence of photosynthesis, autotrophs cease releasing oxygen. Consequently, the oxygen present in the water is consumed by living organisms, drastically reducing the amount dissolved in the medium; this leads to the asphyxiation of many organisms and the possibility of occurring anaerobic fermentation (which increase the medium's acidity).

As most organisms in the ecosystem die, the number of decomposers increases sharply—a trend evidenced by the formation of biofilms on the water's surface.

The activity of these decomposers increases the medium's turbidity, a result of the significant rise in decomposition byproducts within the ecosystem's water.

Arthropods can be observed at the surface of flask B because, without photosynthesis, dissolved oxygen levels drop considerably, becoming insufficient to sustain the organisms' metabolism. Oxygen levels are higher at the surface than at greater depths (since this is the zone where gas exchange with the external environment occurs), making it the area where the highest number of living organisms can be observed under these specific conditions.

Regarding photosynthetic pigments, it is evident that the pigments in the plants used for extraction degrade as the plants' metabolism ceases, with significant changes observable by the end of the study (Fig. 46). This study presents a large number of limitations, notably the absence of replicates, the lack of rigorous measurements (oxygenation, chlorophyll), the use of RGB analysis instead of laboratory methods, and experimental errors, among others.

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